

A checklist of bark and ambrosia beetles (Coleoptera: Scolytidae and Platypodidae) from Siberia and the Russian Far East

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Abstract

Currently, 185 species of the family Scolytidae and three species of the family Platypodidae are recorded from Asian Russia. In total, 99 species of bark beetles are found in Siberia and 168 species in the Russian Far East. Platypodidae are known only from the south of the Russian Far East. Two species of Scolytidae are found in Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug, 13 species in Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug, 19 species in Tyumen Oblast, four species in Kurgan Oblast, three species in Omsk Oblast, 37 species in Tomsk Oblast, 28 species in Novosibirsk Oblast, 32 species in Kemerovo Oblast, 25 species in Altay Krai, 53 species in Altai Republic, 62 species in Krasnoyarsk Krai, 11 species in Republic of Khakassia, 24 species in Tyva Republic, 55 species in Irkutsk Oblast, 61 species in Buryatiya Republic, 40 species in Zabaikalskii Krai, 52 species in Sakha (Yakutia) Republic, 25 species in Kamchatka Oblast, one species in Chukotka Autonomous Okrug, 19 species in Magadan Oblast, 45 species in Amur Oblast, one species in Jewish Autonomous Oblast, 67 species in Khabarovsk Krai, 130 species in Primorsky Krai, 87 species in Sakhalin Is. and 68 species in Kuriles Isl.

Keywords

Curculionoidea, beetles, fauna, distribution, North Asia, Russia

Introduction

The first summarized data about the bark beetles was given by Heyden (1880-1881). The analytical reviews of scolytids were presented by Krivolutskaya (1983) and Yanovskij (1999). The keys to the bark and ambrosia beetles from the Russian Far East were compiled by Krivolutskaya (1996). In 2020, the author (Legalov 2020) published a list of Curculionoidea except the families Scolytidae and Platypodidae from Asian Russia. This is the first review of the bark and ambrosia beetles from Siberia and the Russian Far East.

Material and methods

The studied materials are deposited in the Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals (Novosibirsk), Zoological Institute (St. Petersburg), and some private collections.

The published records of the bark and ambrosia beetles from Siberia and Russian Far East (Heyden 1880–1881; Lavrov 1927; Kiseleva 1928, 1946, 1951, 1952; Kurentsov 1941; Eggers 1942; Frolov 1949; Cherepanov 1952; Stark 1952; Krivolutskaya 1958, 1961, 1965a, 1965b, 1973, 1983, 1996a, 1996b; Rudnev 1958; Sokanovsky 1960; Lindeman 1961; Lurie and Lindeman 1961; Isaev and Tarasova 1965; Nemkova 1965; Galkin 1966; Ivliev and Kononov 1966, 1974; Opanassenko and Kononenko 1966; Krivolutskaya and Kupyanskaya 1970; Averensky 1971, 1999; Kononenko and Opanasenko 1971; Berezhnykh 1979; Nobuchi 1979; Gurov and Dryannykh 1982; Shatilov 1985, 1987; Wood and Bright 1992; Yanovskij 1999; Legalov and Sitnikov 2000; Mandelshtam 2001, 2002; Petrov and Mandelshtam 2002; Izhevsky et al. 2005; Krivets and Chemodanov 2005; Mandelshtam et al. 2007, 2018; Park and Lyu 2007; Bukhhalo et al. 2011, 2014; Kerchev 2011; Knížek 2011; Krivets et al. 2011; Krivets and Vysotina 2011; Petrov 2011, 2018; Akulov and Mandelshtam 2012a, 2012b; Efimov and Legalov 2012; Mandelshtam and Petrov 2016, 2019, 2022; Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017; Kerchev et al. 2019; Petrov et al. 2019; Johnson et al. 2020; Mandelshtam and Sergeev 2020; Petrov and Shamaev 2020; Agafonova et al. 2021; Shamaev 2021; Mandelshtam et al. 2022, etc.) are included.

The high systematics of studied taxa are from the works (Wood 1986, 1993; Zherichin and Egorov 1991; Morimoto and Kojima 2004; Gratshev and Legalov 2014; Legalov 2015).

Abbreviations for the names of federal subjects are follow (Fig. 1): West Siberia: Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug – YAN, Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug – KHM, Tyumen Oblast – TMN, Kurgan Oblast – KURG, Omsk Oblast – OMS, Tomsk Oblast – TOM, Novosibirsk Oblast – NOV, Kemerovo Oblast – KEM, Altay Krai – ALT, Altai Republic – RAL, Krasnoyarsk Krai – KRN, Republic of Khakassia – KHA, Tyva Republic – TUV, East Siberia: Irkutsk Oblast – IRK, Buryatiya Republic – BUR, Zabaikalskii Krai (formerly Chita Oblast) – CHT, Sakha (Yaku-

tia) Republic – YAK, Far East: Kamchatka Oblast – KAM, Chukotka Autonomous Okrug – CHUK, Magadan Oblast – MAG, Amur Oblast – AMUR, EAO – Jewish Autonomous Oblast, Khabarovsk Krai – KHAB, Primorsky Krai – PRIM, Sakhalin Is. – SAKH, Kuriles Isl. – KUR.

Figure 1. Map of the administrative units of studied area.

Results

Superfamily **Curculionoidea** Latreille, 1802

Family **Scolytidae** Latreille, 1806

Subfamily **Hylesininae** Erichson, 1836

Tribe **Hylastini** LeConte, 1876

Genus *Hylastes* Erichson, 1836

ater (Paykull, 1800) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, AMUR.
= *angusticollis* Eggers, 1929

brunneus Erichson, 1836 – TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, BUR, CHT, YAK, KHAB, PRIM.

= *aterrimus* Eggers, 1933

cunicularius Erichson, 1836 (Fig. 2a) – KHM, TMN, TOM, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, PRIM, SAKH.

= *starki* Eggers, 1933

opacus Erichson, 1836 – TMN, TOM, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM.

paralellus Chapuis 1875 – “East Siberia, Far East” [Knížek 2011].

obscurus Chapuis, 1875 – RAL, IRK, YAK, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *plumbeus* Blandford, 1894

= *septentrionalis* Eggers, 1923

Genus *Hylurgops* LeConte, 1876

glabratus (Zetterstedt, 1828) – KHM, TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *paykulli* Duftschmidt, 1825

= *decumanus* Erichson, 1836

= *tenebrosus* Sahlberg, 1836

interstitialis (Chapuis, 1875) – YAK, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

= *imitator* Reitter, 1900

longipilus Reitter, 1894 – IRK, BUR, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

*palliatu*s (Gyllenhal, 1813) – KHM, TMN, NOV, TOM, KEM, RAL, KHA, KRN, BUR, YAK, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *parvus* Eggers, 1933

spessivtsevi Eggers, 1914 – IRK, BUR, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

transbaicalicus Eggers, 1941 – YAK, KAM, KHAB, PRIM.

Tribe **Hylesinini** Erichson, 1836

Genus *Alniphagus* Swaine, 1918

costatus (Blandford, 1894) (Fig. 2b) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *alni* Niisima, 1909

Genus *Hylesinus* Fabricius, 1801

cholodkovskyi Berger, 1916 – PRIM.

cingulatus Blandford, 1894 – KHAB, PRIM.

eos Spessivtsev, 1919 – KHAB, PRIM.

laticollis Blandford, 1894 – KHAB, PRIM.

= *striatus* Eggers, 1933

= *pravdini* Stark, 1936

nobilis Blandford, 1894 – PRIM.
 = *shabliovskiyi* Kurenzov, 1941
mandshuricus Eggers, 1922 – PRIM.
tristis Blandford, 1894 (Fig. 2c) – PRIM.
 = *lubarskiyi* Stark, 1936

Genus *Longulus* Krivolutskaya, 1968

elatus (Niisima, 1913) (Fig. 2d) – KUR.

Tribe **Hylurgini** Gistel, 1848

Genus *Dendroctonus* Erichson, 1836

micans (Kugelann, 1794) (Fig. 2e) – KHM, KURG, NOV, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Genus *Hylurgus* Latreille, 1806

ligniperda (Fabricius, 1787) – ALT.

Genus *Tomicus* Latreille, 1802

minor (Hartig, 1834) – TMN, NOV, TOM, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

pilifer (Spessivtsev, 1919) – KHAB, PRIM.

piniperda (Linnaeus, 1758) – TMN, NOV, TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, AMUR, PRIM.

puellus (Reitter, 1894) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *puellus* f. *orientalis* Krivolutskaya, 1956

= *starki* Eggers, 1929

Genus *Xylechinus* Chapuis, 1869

bergeri Spessivtsev, 1919 – PRIM

pilosus (Ratzeburg, 1837) – NOV, TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, YAK, MAG, KAM, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Tribe **Hyorrhynchini** Hopkins, 1915

Genus *Pseudohyorrhynchus* Murayama, 1950

wadai Murayama, 1950 (Fig. 2f) – KUR.

= *wadai kurilensis* Krivolutskaya, 1956

Tribe **Diamerini** Hagedorn, 1909

Genus *Sphaerotrypes* Blandford, 1894

imitans Eggers, 1926 – PRIM.

juglansis Krivolutskaya, 1970 – PRIM.

Tribe **Phloeotribini** Chapuis, 1869

Genus *Phloeotribus* Latreille, 1797

spinulosus (Rey, 1883) – KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, SAKH.

Tribe **Polygraphini** Chapuis, 1869

Genus *Carphoborus* Eichhoff, 1864

cholodkovskiyi Spessivtsev, 1916 – NOV, TOM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR.

jurinskii Eggers, 1910 – IRK, YAK.

rossicus Semenov, 1902 – KEM, KRN.

teplouchovi Spessivtsev, 1916 – NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR.

Genus *Polygraphus* Erichson, 1836

abietis Kurentsov, 1941 – KHAB, PRIM.

gracilis Niisima, 1909 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

horyurensis Murayama, 1937 – SAKH.

jezoensis Niisima, 1909 – KAM, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

kisoensis Niisima, 1941 – SAKH.

nigrielytris Niisima, 1913 – KAM, SAKH, KUR.

polygraphus (Linnaeus, 1758) – TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *pubescens* Fabricius, 1792

= *griseus* Eggers, 1932

proximus Blandford, 1894 – NOV, TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, KHA, IRK, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *abietis* Kurenzov, 1941

= *horyurensis* Murayama, 1937

= *laticollis* Eggers, 1926

punctifrons Thomson, 1886 – TOM, RAL, KRN, YAK, KAM, SAKH.

= *seriatus* Reitter, 1913
shariensis Niisima, 1941 – SAKH, KUR.
ssiori Niisima, 1909 – SAKH, KUR.
subopacus Thomson, 1871 – TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, KAM,
 AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
 = *sachalinensis* Eggers, 1926

Subfamily **Scolytinae** Latreille, 1806

Tribe **Scolytini** Latreille, 1806

Genus *Scolytus* Geoffroy, 1762

aratus Blandford, 1884 – AMUR, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
 = *aequipunctatus* Niisima, 1905
 = *brevipennis* Kurenzov, 1941
 = *intermedius* Kurenzov, 1941
butovitschi Stark, 1936 – KRN, BUR, PRIM.
 = *butovitschi* Eggers, 1942
chikisanii Niisima, 1905 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
 = *curviventralis* Niisima, 1905
 = *mandschuricus* Schedl, 1941
claviger Blandford, 1894 – KHAB, PRIM.
 = *platystylus* Wichmann, 1915
dahuricus Chapuis, 1869 – CHT, AMUR, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
 = *possyeti* Stark, 1938
esuriens Blandford, 1894 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
 = *sachalinensis* Michalski, 1964
jacobsoni (Spessivtsev, 1919) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.
 = *rimskii* Kurenzov, 1941
japonicus Chapuis, 1875 – BUR, CHT, KHAB, PRIM.
 = *confusus* Eggers, 1922
 = *mandli* Eggers, 1922
 = *starki* Kurenzov, 1941
 = *subconfusus* Eggers, 1941
 = *ussuriensis* Kurenzov, 1941
kirschii Skalitzky, 1876 – ALT.
 = *fasciatus* Reitter, 1890
koltzei Reitter, 1894 – KHAB, PRIM.
 = *vexator* Reitter, 1913
kononovi Kurenzov, 1941 – PRIM.

mali (Bechstein, 1805) – KURG, BUR, “Western Siberia” [Stark 1952], “Far East” [Knížek 2011].

= *pruni* Ratzeburg, 1837)

= *pyri* Ratzeburg, 1837

= *bicallosus* Eggers, 1933

morawitzi Semenov, 1902 – NOV, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *pini* Eggers, 1942

nunbergi Michalski, 1964 – PRIM.

pubescens Stark, 1936 – PRIM.

ratzeburgi Janson, 1856 (Figs. 2g-h) – KHM, TMN, OMS, NOV, TOM, ALT, KEM, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *amurensis* Eggers, 1908

= *sahlbergi* Eggers, 1912

= *sibiricus* Eggers, 1922

= *lineatus* Kurenzov, 1941

rugulosus (Mueller, 1818) – KURG, TOM, ALT, “Transbaicalia” [Yanovskij 1999]

= *mediterraneus* Eggers, 1922

= *caucasicus* Butovitsch, 1929

= *rugulosus samarkandicus* Butovitsch, 1929

= *manglissiensis* Lezhava, 1940

= *taxicola* Lezhava, 1941

= *rugulosus intermedius* Sokanovskii, 1960

schevyrewi Semenov, 1902 – NOV, ALT, KHA, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, PRIM.

= *transcaspicus* Eggers, 1922

= *sinensis* Eggers, 1910

scolytus (Fabricius, 1775) – IRK, “Western Siberia” [Yanovskij 1999].

= *destructor* Olivier, 1795

= *fuchsi* Reitter, 1913

semenovi (Spessivtsev, 1919) – BUR, KHAB, PRIM.

ventrosus Schevyrew, 1890 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR, “East Siberia” [Petrov et al. 2019].

= *grandis* Kurenzov, 1941

= *ventricosus* Schevyrew, 1897

= *trispinosus* Strohmeyer, 1908

Tribe **Scolytoplatypodini** Blandford, 1893

Genus *Scolytoplatypus* Schaufuss, 1891

daimio Blandford, 1893 (Fig. 3a) – SAKH, KUR.

mikado Blandford, 1893 (Figs. 2i-j) – SAKH, KUR.

tycon Blandford, 1893 (Figs. 2k-l) – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Figure 2. Representatives of Scolytidae: a – *Hylastes cunicularius*, b – *Alniphagus costatus*, c – *Hylesinus tristis*, d – *Longulus elatus*, e – *Dendroctonus micans*, f – *Pseudohyorrhynchus wadai*, g – *Scolytus ratzeburgi*, female, h – *S. ratzeburgi*, male, i – *Scolytoplatypus mikado*, male, j – *S. mikado*, female, k – *S. tycon*, male, l – *S. tycon*, female. Photos from www.zin.ru/Animalia/Coleoptera. Author K.V. Makarov.

Tribe **Micracidini** LeConte, 1876

Genus *Pseudothysanoes* Blackman, 1920

= *Gretschkinia* Sokanovskii, 1958

modestus (Murayama, 1940) – “Transbaicalia” [Krivolutskaya 1996].

= *mongolica* Sokanovskii, 1958

Tribe **Ipini** Bedel, 1888

Genus *Ips* De Geer, 1775

acuminatus (Gyllenhal, 1827) – TMN, NOV, TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

amitinus (Eichhoff, 1871) – TOM, KEM.

duplicatus (Sahlberg, 1836) – KHM, TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

hauseri Reitter, 1894 – KRN, “South Altai” [Stark 1952].

= *ussuriensis* Reitter, 1913

sexdentatus (Boerner, 1767) – KHM, KURG, TMN, NOV, TOM, KEM, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.

subelongatus (Motschulsky, 1860) – NOV, KEM, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, CHUK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

typographus (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 3b) – KHM, TMN, NOV, TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Orthotomicus* Ferrari, 1867

golovjankoi Pjatnitzky, 1930 – CHT, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

laricis (Fabricius, 1792) – TMN, TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

proximus (Eichhoff, 1867) – TMN, NOV, TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, PRIM.

starki Spessivtsev, 1926 – RAL, KRN, BUR, KAM, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

suturalis (Gyllenhal, 1827) – YAN, KHM, TMN, NOV, TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *nigritus* Gyllenhal, 1827

Genus *Pityogenes* Bedel, 1888

bidentatus (Herbst, 1784) – NOV, TOM, ALT, RAL, KEM, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

chalcographus (Linnaeus, 1761) – KHM, TMN, OMS, NOV, TOM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

conjunctus (Reitter, 1887) – TMN, TOM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, MAG, PRIM, KUR.

= *baicalicus* Eggers, 1933

foveolatus Eggers, 1926 – BUR, CHT, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

irkutensis Eggers, 1910 – TMN, TOM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, AMUR, PRIM.

= *monacensis* Fuchs, 1911

quadridens (Hartig, 1834) – TOM, ALT, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR.

rudnevi Sokanovskii, 1959 – PRIM.

saalasi Eggers, 1914 – RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK.

seirindensis Murayama, 1929 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *aizawai* Kono, 1938

= *nitidus* Eggers, 1941

Genus *Pityokteines* Fuchs, 1911

curvidens (Germar, 1824) – YAK.

Tribe **Dryocoetini** Lindemann, 1877

Genus *Dryocoetes* Eichhoff, 1864

aceris Krivolutskaya, 1968 – KUR.

alni (Georg, 1856) – RAL, KRN, IRK.

autographus (Ratzeburg, 1837) (Fig. 3c) – YAN, TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *suecicus* Eggers, 1923

baikalicus Reitter, 1899 – NOV, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, AMUR, KHAB, SAKH, KUR.

infuscatus Murayama, 1937 – BUR, CHT, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *orientalis* Kurenzov, 1941

= *orientalis* var. *pilosiusculus* Kurenzov, 1948

hectographus Reitter, 1913 – KHM, TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

krivolutzkajae Mandelshtam, 2001 – KAM.

pini Niisima, 1909 – BUR, CHT, SAKH.

cerasi Eggers, 1942 – PRIM.

= *cerasi* Stark, 1950

padi Kurenzov, 1941 – KHAB, PRIM.

= *padi* Stark, 1952

rugicollis Eggers, 1926 – AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

striatus Eggers, 1933 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *abietinus* Kono et Tamanuki, 1939

uniseriatus Eggers, 1926 – SAKH.

ussuriensis Eggers, 1933 – MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR, “Western Siberia” [Knížek 2011].

= *rugulosus* Eggers, 1933

Genus *Lymantor* Lovendal, 1889

aceris (Lindemann, 1875) – BUR, PRIM.

coryli (Perris, 1853) – IRK, BUR, YAK, “Western Siberia, Far East” [Alonso-Zaragoza et al. 2017].

Genus *Taphrorychus* Eichhoff, 1878

carpini (Kurenzov, 1941) – PRIM.

= *carpini* Eggers, 1942

= *carpini* Stark, 1952

Tribe **Crypturgini** LeConte, 1876

Genus *Crypturgus* Erichson, 1836

cinereus (Herbst, 1793) – NOV, TOM, KEM, ALT, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

hispidulus Thomson, 1870 – TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, BUR, CHT, YAK, KAM, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

pusillus (Gyllenhal, 1813) – TOM, KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

subcribrosus Eggers, 1933 – KRN, PRIM, SAKH, “Eastern Siberia” [Knížek 2011].

tuberosus Niisima, 1909 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

Tribe **Xyloterini** LeConte, 1876

Genus *Indocryphalus* Eggers, 1939

aceris (Niisima, 1910) (Fig. 3d) – KHAB, PRIM.

pubipennis (Blandford, 1894) – “SAKH, KUR” [Krivolutskaya 1996].

Genus *Trypodendron* Stephens, 1830

laeve Eggers, 1939 – KRN.

lineatum (Olivier, 1795) – KHM, TMN, TOM, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, MAG, KAM, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

=*granulatum* Eggers, 1933

niponicum Blandford, 1894 – BUR, MAG, KAM, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

proximum Niisima, 1909 (Fig. 3e) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

signatum (Fabricius, 1787) – NOV, KEM, RAL, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, PRIM, SAKH.

=*suturale* Eggers, 1933

Tribe **Xyleborini** LeConte, 1876

Genus *Anisandrus* Ferrari, 1867

apicalis Blandford, 1894 – PRIM, KUR (Kunashir).

dispar (Fabricius, 1792) (Figs. 3g-h) – TMN, TOM, OMS, NOV, KEM, ALT, RAL, KHA, KRN, TUV, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *aequalis* Reitter, 1913

maiche Stark, 1936 – PRIM, KUR, “Western Siberia” [Krivolutskaya 1996], “Eastern Siberia” [Knížek 2011].

Genus *Cnestus* Sampson, 1911

mutilatus (Blandford, 1894) – PRIM.

Genus *Cyclorhipidion* Hagedorn, 1912

bodoanus Reitter, 1913 – EAO, PRIM. “Eastern Siberia” [Stark 1952].

= *punctulatus* Kurenzov, 1948

japonicus (Nobuchi, 1981) – PRIM.

pelliculosum (Eichhoff, 1878) – PRIM.

=*starki* Nunberg, 1956

= *quercus* Kurenzov, 1948

Genus *Microperus* Wood, 1980

molestus Park et Smith, 2020 – PRIM.

Genus *Xyleborinus* Reitter, 1913

attenuatus (Eichhoff, 1876) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.

= *alni* Niisima, 1909

saxesenii (Ratzeburg, 1837) – TUV, BUR, YAK, KAM, PRIM, SAKH, KUR, “Western Siberia” [Knížek 2011].

Figure 3. Representatives of Scolytidae: a – *Scolytoplatypus daimio*, male, b – *Ips typographus*, c – *Dryocoetes autographus*, d – *Indocryphalus aceris*, e – *Trypodendron proximum*, f – *Xyleborus seriatus*, g – *Anisandrus dispar*, female, h – *A. dispar*, male, i – *Ernoporicus insularum*. Photos from www.zin.ru/Animalia/Coleoptera. Author K.V. Makarov.

Genus *Xyleborus* Eichhoff, 1864

cryptographus (Ratzeburg, 1837) – KRN, “Altai” [Yanovskij 1999], “Western Siberia, Far East” [Knížek 2011].

seriatus Blandford, 1894 (Fig. 3f) – PRIM.

= *orientalis* Eggers, 1933

Genus *Xylosandrus* Reitter, 1913

germanus (Blandford, 1894) – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

Tribe **Cryphalini** Lindemann, 1877Genus *Allernoporus* Kurenzov, 1941

euonymi Kurenzov, 1941 – PRIM.

Genus *Cryphalus* Erichson, 1836

asperatus (Gyllenhal, 1813) – TOM, KRN, IRK, “Far East” [Knížek 2011].

= *abietis* Ratzeburg, 1837

carpini Berger, 1916 – PRIM.

= *carpinivorus* Murayama, 1930

coryli Stark, 1936 – PRIM.

exiguus Blandford, 1894 – SAKH, KUR.

kurenzovi Stark, 1936 – AMUR, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *punctulatus* Eggers, 1942

= *ussuriensis* Eggers, 1942

kurilensis Krivolutskaya, 1968 – KUR.

laricis Niisima, 1909 – SAKH.

latus Eggers, 1929 – BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, “Western Siberia” [Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017].

= *premayaensis* Murayama, 1943

longus (Eggers, 1926) – KAM, MAG, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

= *alni* Krivolutskaya, 1958

malus Niisima, 1909 – SAKH, KUR.

= *padi* Krivolutskaya, 1958

mandschuricus Eggers, 1929 – KHAB, PRIM.

nataliyae Mandelshtam et Petrov, 2022 – SAKH.

piceae (Ratzeburg, 1837) – KHAB, PRIM.

= *orientalis* Eggers, 1911

piceus Eggers, 1926 – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH, KUR.

pruni Eggers, 1929 – PRIM, SAKH.

redikorzevi Berger, 1916 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
saltuarius Weise, 1891 – RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, CHT, YAK, AMUR, KHAB, PRIM.
scopiger Berger, 1916 – PRIM.
sichotensis Kurenzov, 1941 – KHAB, PRIM.
viburni Stark, 1936 – PRIM.
= *viburni* Eggers, 1942

Genus *Eidophelus* Eichhoff, 1875

imitans Eichhoff, 1875 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
= *elegans* Krivolutskaya, 1958

Genus *Ernoporicus* Berger, 1917

corni (Kurenzov, 1941) – KHAB, PRIM, SAKH.
insularum (Krivolutskaya, 1968) (Fig. 3i) – KUR.
= *krivolutskayae* Wood, 1992
semenovi (Kurenzov, 1941) – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
spessivtzevi Berger, 1916 – PRIM, SAKH, KUR.
zachvatkini (Krivolutskaya, 1958) – SAKH, KUR.

Genus *Ernoporus* Thomson, 1859

tiliae (Panzer, 1793) – PRIM, “Western Siberia” [Stark 1952].
= *eggersi* Stark, 1936
= *starki* Eggers, 1942

Genus *Hypothenemus* Westwood, 1834

atomus Hopkins, 1915 – PRIM.
margaritae Petrov and Shamaev, 2020 – PRIM.

Genus *Procryphalus* Hopkins, 1915

fraxini (Berger, 1916) – KHAB, PRIM.

Genus *Trypophloeus* Fairmaire, 1868

alni (Lindemann, 1875) – RAL, KRN, IRK, MAG, KAM, PRIM, SAKH.
binodulus (Ratzeburg, 1837) – NOV, KRN, ALT, RAL, PRIM, SAKH.
= *berezinae* Stark, 1952
= *kurenzovi* Nunberg, 1956
= *kurenzovi* Schedl, 1959
= *populi* Kurenzov, 1941

=*grothii* Hagedorn, 1904

bispinulus Eggers, 1927 – RAL, BUR, PRIM.

dejevi Stark, 1936 – BUR, KAM, MAG, PRIM, SAKH, “Western Siberia” [Knížek 2011].

= *dejevi* Eggers, 1942

= *niger* Stark, 1936

Tribe **Corthylini** LeConte, 1876

Subtribe **Pityophthorina** Eichhoff, 1878

Genus *Pityophthorus* Eichhoff, 1864

abietinus Wood, 1989 – PRIM.

= *abietis* Kurenzov, 1941

= *kurentzovi* Krivolutskaya, 1996

glabratus Eichhoff, 1878 – RAL, KRN.

jucundus Blandford, 1894 – SAKH.

lapponicus Kurenzov, 1941 – PRIM, “Eastern Siberia” [Yanovskij 1999].

= *lapponicus* Stark, 1952

lichtensteinii (Ratzeburg, 1837) – KEM, RAL, KRN, IRK, YAK, AMUR, KUR.

= *rossicus* Eggers, 1915

micrographus (Linnaeus, 1758) – RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR, YAK, AMUR.

morosovi Spessivtsev, 1926 – RAL, KRN, IRK, BUR.

pini Kurenzov, 1941 – KRN, IRK, YAK, PRIM.

sachalinensis Krivolutskaya, 1956 – SAKH.

sichotensis Kurenzov, 1941 – KEM, IRK, PRIM.

traegardhi Spessivtsev, 1921 – RAL, KRN, IRK, YAK, “Far East” [Knížek 2011].

Subtribe **Corthyliina** LeConte, 1876

Genus *Monarthrum* Kirsch, 1866

meuseli (Reitter, 1905) – KRN.

Family **Platypodidae** Shuckard, 1840

Subfamily **Platypodinae** Shuckard, 1840

Tribe **Platypodini** Shuckard, 1840

Genus *Platypus* Herbst, 1793

koryoensis (Murayama, 1930) – PRIM.

quercivorus (Murayama, 1925) – PRIM.

Genus *Treptoplatypus* Schedl, 1972

severini (Blandford, 1894) (Fig. 4) – PRIM, KUR.

Currently, 185 species of the family Scolytidae and three species of the family Platypodidae are recorded from Asian Russia, 99 species of bark beetles are found in Siberia and 168 species in the Russian Far East. Platypodidae are known from the of the the Russian Far East. Two species are found in Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug, 13 species in Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug, 19 species in Tyumen Oblas, four species in Kurgan Oblast, three species in Omsk Oblast, 37 species in Tomsk Oblast, 28 species in Novosibirsk Oblast, 32 species in Kemerovo Oblast, 25 species in Altay Krai, 53 species in Altai Republic, 62 species in Krasnoyarsk Krai, 11 species in Republic of Khakassia, 24 species in Tyva Republic, 55 species in Irkutsk Oblast, 61 species in Buryatiya Republic, 40 species in Zabaikalskii Krai, 52 species in Sakha (Yakutia) Republic, 25 species in Kamchatka Oblast, one species in Chukotka Autonomous Okrug, 19 species in Magadan Oblast, 45 species in Amur Oblast, one species in Jewish Autonomous Oblast, 67 species in Khabarovsk Krai, 130 species in Primorsky Krai, 87 species in Sakhalin Is. and 68 species in Kuriles Isl.

Figure 4. *Treptoplatypus severini*: a – male, b – female. Photos from www.zin.ru/Animalia/Coleoptera. Author K.V. Makarov.

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